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Influence of Demographic Variables on Marital Satisfaction of Undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of demographic variables on marital satisfaction among undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated and tested to guide the study. The study adopted the analytical survey research design. The population comprised of all married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt City, Nigeria. A sample size of 400 was drawn out randomly using the Taro Yamane Formula. To select this sample, the convenience volunteer non-probability sampling technique was utilized. A researcher developed instrument titled “Marital Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ)” was administered to gather data. In order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument, a reliability test was conducted on 100 undergraduates whom were not part of the sample of the main study. Data were collated and analysed for reliability using Cronbach Alpha correlation co-efficient. The reliability co-efficient of .928 was realized. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions, while the Chi-square goodness of fit test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that; educational attainment, length of marriage and presence or absence of children had significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates. Based on the findings it was recommended among others that; educational goals and aspirations should be integrated into discussions and decision-making processes within relationships.

Keywords: demographic variables, marital satisfaction, marriage

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is a complex institution that brings together two individuals in a profound partnership. It is a union laden with tradition and meaning, representing a commitment to shared values, goals, and responsibilities. The dynamics within a marriage can vary greatly, shaped by factors like communication, trust, and mutual respect. When couples navigate challenges with empathy, compromise, and understanding, they tend to experience greater satisfaction in their relationship, deepening their connection and enriching their shared life journey. Healthy and cohesive marital bonds are essential not only for the well-being of individuals but also for the welfare of children and consequently, for the broader community. Conversely, dissatisfying and tense marital connections contribute to heightened psychological distress and dissatisfaction within the marriage.

Marital satisfaction entails the level of contentment or happiness experienced within a marriage. Tavakol, Nasrabadi, Moghadam, Salehiniya, and Rezae (2016) highlight it as a key measure for assessing the well-being and durability of a marital union. Beyond the mere existence of marriage, what truly matters is the

fulfilment and contentment felt by the partners involved. It serves as a significant area of exploration as it offers a comprehensive assessment of the quality of a marriage, reflecting both the happiness and functionality within it. From an evolutionary standpoint, marital satisfaction can be seen as a psychological state governed by mechanisms that weigh the advantages and drawbacks of marriage for an individual (Zainah, Nasir, Hashim & Yusof, 2012).

Girma (2020) avers that various psychosocial and socio-demographic elements have the potential to influence the behaviours, thoughts, emotions, communication patterns, and overall interpersonal dynamics within a marital relationship. When evaluating marital satisfaction, it's crucial to consider these diverse factors. Among the variables to be considered are age, duration of marriage, educational background, employment status, history of previous marriages, gender, presence or absence of children, personality characteristics, attachment styles, and psychological issues, among others.

Other factors influencing marital satisfaction encompass the demonstration of affection between spouses and the extent of their shared time. Moreover, factors pertinent to marital contentment, as perceived by spouses, encompass sexual fulfilment, the distribution of household responsibilities, and perspectives on gender roles (Bahrami, Armanmehr, Rezaeian, Alami & Kharazmi, 2021). For this research, our emphasis will be on exploring the effects of socio-demographic variables such as the duration of marriage, the educational level attained by spouses, and the presence or absence of children.

Educational attainment denotes the highest level of education achieved by an individual, and research indicates its association with marital satisfaction, often serving as a predictor (Tavakol *et al.*, 2016). Studies in Malaysia have revealed that couples with higher education levels tend to report greater marital satisfaction and improved mental health compared to those with lower levels of education (Madanianan & Syed, 2013). This phenomenon is attributed to the enhanced social functioning observed among highly educated individuals. Indeed, better-educated couples often possess a deeper comprehension of life's realities, which equips them to effectively address challenges and mitigate conflicts (Tavakol *et al.*, 2016). However, contrary findings suggest that women with higher educational backgrounds may be more prone to divorce (Chen, 2012), and some studies even suggest that highly educated women tend to have less fulfilling marriages (Ahangar, Juhari, Yaacob & Talib, 2016).

Children exert significant influence on the lives of married couples, inevitably impacting their marital relationship either positively or negatively. The presence of young children in particular has been linked to decreased marital satisfaction, often attributed to the reduction in couples' available time together (Bayle, Ayalew & Yime, 2017). Another factor affecting marital satisfaction is the duration of marriage, with initial high levels of satisfaction declining over time. While some studies demonstrate a negative correlation between marriage duration and marital satisfaction, others indicate that with increased years of marriage, marital adjustment improves (Zainah *et al.*, 2012). Researchers posit that couples who surpass the ten-year mark have likely overcome initial adaptation challenges, leading to reduced psychological distress and stress (Tavakol *et al.*, 2016).

Statement of the Problem

Marriage is an interesting social activity and it is not unusual to see intending couples so happy about the decision to be married. But this is just a step in the long process of the union between a man and a woman that is influenced by various factors. An individual that is dissatisfied in marriage will be destabilized psychologically and emotionally and this could affect their social functioning and efficiency in day-to-day activities. The researcher feels for students, the workload of being unsatisfied in marriage would be more than the usual as the person would struggle with managing the home, adjusting in school and in some cases even at work. Satisfaction in marriage can have some influence on the academic performance of married students and on their psychological and social adjustment in the school. Undergraduates in Rivers State University are no exception as it is common to see both females and males with rings on their fingers indicating marriage. The females can be seen with babies and infants in lectures and exams. Basically, satisfaction in marriage is key to their normal functioning and in the current study the researcher aims to find out how demographic variables influence the process of marital satisfaction among married undergraduates.

Research Questions

The following research questions shall be answered to guide the study;

1. What is the influence of educational attainment of spouse on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt?
2. What is the influence of length of marriage on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates?
3. What is the influence of presence or absence of children on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates?

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses shall be tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. Educational attainment of spouse has no significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.
2. Length of marriage has no significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates.
3. Presence or absence of children has no significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the analytical survey research design. The population comprised of all married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt City, Nigeria. A sample size of 400 was drawn out randomly using the Taro Yamane Formula. To select this sample, the convenience volunteer non-probability sampling technique was utilized. A researcher developed instrument titled “Marital Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ)” was administered to gather data. In order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument, a reliability test was conducted on 100 undergraduates whom were not part of the sample of the main study. Data were collated and analysed for reliability using Cronbach Alpha correlation coefficient. The reliability co-efficient of .928 was realized. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions, while the Chi-square goodness of fit test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question 1: *What is the influence of educational attainment of spouse on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt?*

Table 1: Analysis of Influence of Educational Attainment of Spouse on Marital Satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	The education level of my spouse contributes to my overall marital satisfaction.	100	180	64	56	2.81	.968	Accepted
2	It is important to me that my spouse shares similar educational values and aspirations.	200	144	24	32	3.28	.896	Accepted
3	My long-term goals align with those of my spouse in terms of education and career.	156	180	44	20	3.18	.818	Accepted
4	My spouse and I share similar educational interests.	112	204	52	32	2.99	.855	Accepted
5	Educational compatibility between spouses is important for marital satisfaction.	120	160	80	40	2.90	.945	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		$\bar{X} = 3.032$		SD = .8964		Accepted		

Table 1 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 1 to 5 are 2.81, 3.28, 3.18, 2.99, and 2.90 with corresponding standard deviations of .968, .896, .818, .855, and .945 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.032 with the cluster standard deviation of .8964 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that educational attainment of spouse has influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Research Question 2: *What is the influence of length of marriage on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt?*

Table 2: Analysis of Influence of Length of Marriage on Marital Satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	The length of our marriage has a significant impact on our marital satisfaction.	320	60	20	0	3.75	.537	Accepted
7	Over time, I have seen improvements in our marital satisfaction.	160	180	40	20	3.20	.813	Accepted
8	Our communication has become more effective as our marriage has progressed.	128	120	80	72	2.76	1.089	Accepted
9	Shared experiences over the years have strengthened our marital bond.	120	240	32	8	3.18	.655	Accepted
10	We continue to create new shared goals and aspirations in our marriage.	140	164	56	40	3.01	.945	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.18$ SD= .8078								Accepted

Table 2 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10 are 3.75, 3.20, 2.76, 3.18, and 3.01 with corresponding standard deviations of .537, .813, 1.089, .655, and .945 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.18 with the cluster standard deviation of .8078 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that length of marriage has influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Research Question 3: *What is the influence of presence or absence of children on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt?*

Table 3: Analysis of Influence of Presence or Absence of Children on Marital Satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	The presence of children in our marriage has a significant impact on our marital satisfaction.	120	160	80	40	2.90	.945	Accepted
12	I believe having children positively contributes to our marital satisfaction.	320	60	20	0	3.75	.537	Accepted
13	We effectively communicate about parenting decisions and responsibilities.	160	180	40	20	3.20	.813	Accepted
14	The shared experiences of raising children strengthen our marital bond.	183	139	42	36	3.17	.946	Accepted
15	We find joy and fulfilment in the shared responsibility of parenting.	170	172	1	57	3.14	.990	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.232$ SD= .8462								Accepted

Table 3 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 16 to 20 are 2.90, 3.75, 3.20, 3.17, and 3.14 with corresponding standard deviations of .945, .537, .813, .946, and .990 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.232 with the cluster standard deviation of .8462 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that presence or absence of children has influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Chi-square (X^2) was used to test the responses of respondents at .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Educational attainment of spouse has no significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Table 4: Chi-square Test of Influence of Educational Attainment of Spouse on Marital Satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	96.320	.000	Sig.
SA	100	100.0					
A	180	100.0					
D	64	100.0					
SD	56	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 4 revealed that $\chi^2 = 96.320$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that educational attainment of spouse has no significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt therefore, not accepted. This implies that educational attainment of spouse has significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Hypothesis 2

Length of marriage has no significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Table 5: Chi-square Test of Influence of Length of Marriage on Marital Satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	200.00	.000	Sig.
SA	160	100.0					
A	180	100.0					
D	40	100.0					
SD	20	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 5 revealed that $\chi^2 = 200.00$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that length of marriage has no significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt is therefore, not accepted. This implies that length of marriage has significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Hypothesis 3

Presence or absence of children has no significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Table 6: Chi-square Test of Influence of Presence or Absence of Children on Marital Satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	158.700	.000	Sig.
SA	183	100.0					
A	139	100.0					
D	42	100.0					
SD	36	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 6 revealed that $\chi^2 = 158.700$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that presence or absence of children has no significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt is therefore, not accepted. This implies that presence or absence of children has significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this research is organized around the research questions and hypotheses. The four null hypotheses that were postulated and tested were all rejected.

The first finding revealed that educational attainment of spouse has significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. This implies that the level of education acquired by a spouse influences how satisfied the spouse and their partner feels in the marriage. The findings of the study underscore the pivotal role that educational attainment of a spouse plays in shaping the marital satisfaction of married undergraduates. Education not only equips individuals with knowledge and skills but also influences their perspectives, aspirations, and communication styles. When partners possess similar educational backgrounds, they are more likely to share common interests, understand each other's challenges, and navigate life's complexities together with greater synergy. In a similar vein, Mirhosseini, Nasirian, Bastami and Zamani-Alavijeh (2020) found in a study that demographic variables, such as spouse's education and age, income, the individual's occupation, and the fate of parents' marriage can affect marital satisfaction positively or negatively. Moreover, discrepancies in educational levels may lead to disparities in power dynamics, decision-making processes, and mutual understanding, potentially posing challenges to marital harmony. Therefore, this study highlights the importance of considering educational compatibility alongside other factors in fostering fulfilling and sustainable relationships among married undergraduates.

The second finding revealed that length of marriage has significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates. This implies that the duration of marriage of spouses influences how satisfied the spouses feel in the marriage. The study's findings illuminate the substantial impact of the length of marriage on the marital satisfaction of married undergraduates. As relationships mature over time, couples often navigate through various phases characterized by evolving dynamics, challenges, and milestones. The length of marriage serves as a proxy for the depth of shared experiences, the resilience of the partnership, and the efficacy of coping mechanisms developed over time. Similarly, Zainah *et al.*, (2012) also found that length of marriage influenced the level of marital satisfaction of couples. In the initial stages, newlywed couples may experience a honeymoon phase characterized by intense affection and excitement. However, as the relationship progresses, they encounter inevitable trials that test their commitment and compatibility. Weathering these storms together can strengthen the bond between partners, fostering deeper understanding, trust, and emotional intimacy. Contrastingly, Oniye, Mustapha, Ajiboye and Alade (2015) in a study found that length of marriage, age, educational attainment among other demographic variables were not jointly and significantly correlated with marital satisfaction. Moreso, prolonged periods of dissatisfaction or unresolved conflicts may erode marital satisfaction over

time. Thus, the length of marriage emerges as a critical factor influencing the overall well-being and contentment of married undergraduates in their relationships.

The third finding revealed that presence or absence of children has significant influence on marital satisfaction of married undergraduates. This implies that having or not having children influences how satisfied the spouse and their partner feels in the marriage. The study's findings shed light on the profound impact of the presence or absence of children on the marital satisfaction of married undergraduates. Parenthood introduces a myriad of joys, responsibilities, and stressors that can fundamentally reshape the dynamics of a relationship (Tavakol, Nasrabadi, Moghadam & Salehiniya, 2019). For couples with children, the challenges of balancing academic pursuits, parenting duties, and maintaining a healthy marital bond can be particularly demanding. The arrival of children often necessitates adjustments in priorities, time management, and communication patterns, which may either deepen the connection between partners or strain their relationship. Conversely, childless couples may enjoy greater freedom, flexibility, and spontaneity in their daily lives, potentially fostering stronger marital satisfaction. However, the absence of children could also lead to feelings of unfulfilled expectations or societal pressures, especially for those aspiring to parenthood. Hutabarat and Himawan (2023) in a study aver that child ownership is not the predominant determinant of marital satisfaction. The authors maintain that, whether due to choices or circumstances, deciding to have or not have children brings its own set of unique stressors. This indicates that neither condition (i.e., having or not having children) can be universally considered better than the other. While couples with children perceive low societal pressure, they concurrently grapple with the significant challenges associated with raising children.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study underscores the multifaceted nature of marital satisfaction, revealing that it is influenced by a combination of factors including the educational attainment of both spouses, the duration of their marriage, and the presence or absence of children. These findings highlight the importance of considering various socio-demographic variables when assessing marital well-being. Couples with higher levels of education may possess better problem-solving skills and a deeper understanding of life's complexities, potentially contributing to greater satisfaction in their relationships. Additionally, the duration of marriage emerges as a significant factor, with satisfaction levels fluctuating over time but potentially stabilizing after an initial adjustment period. Moreover, the presence of children introduces unique challenges, such as time constraints, which can impact the dynamics of the marital relationship. Overall, recognizing and understanding these influences can aid in the development of targeted interventions and support systems aimed at enhancing marital satisfaction and promoting healthy long-term relationships.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Educational goals and aspirations should be integrated into discussions and decision-making processes within relationships. This could involve couples openly discussing their educational paths, supporting each other's academic endeavours, and recognizing the potential impact of educational disparities on relationship dynamics. Additionally, couples could explore ways to address any challenges or discrepancies in educational attainment through communication, mutual respect, and shared goals for personal and relational growth.
2. Regularly investing time and effort into nurturing the marital bond through activities such as date nights, shared hobbies, and meaningful conversations can help sustain marital satisfaction over time. Additionally, couples may benefit from seeking out resources such as counselling or relationship education to navigate challenges and maintain a strong foundation as their marriage evolves.
3. Couples should engage in open and honest discussions about their desires and expectations regarding parenthood. It is crucial for couples to consider the potential impact of having children

on their relationship dynamics, lifestyle, and future goals. Whether they choose to have children or not, maintaining effective communication, mutual support, and shared decision-making can help navigate the complexities of family planning and ensure that both partners' needs and priorities are respected and addressed within the relationship.

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